

IDENTIFICATION OF MEANS AND METHODS OF EDUCATING THE REACTION OF CHOICE IN BLIND AND WEAK SIGHTED ADOLESCENT JUDOKAS

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Abstract This article provides theoretical information on the quality of agility and the importance of the selection reaction of judo fighters in solo training, as well as how to educate it.

Keywords Judo, blind, and weak-sighted, teenagers educate the reaction of choice, general physical fitness, special physical fitness, physical qualities, agility, speed.

ВЫЯВЛЕНИЕ СРЕДСТВ И МЕТОДОВ ВОСПИТАНИЯ ИЗБИРАТЕЛЬНОЙ РЕАКЦИИ У НЕЗРЯЧИХ И СЛАБОВИДЯЩИХ ДЗЮДОИСТОВ ПОДРОСТКОВ

Аннотация В этой статье излагается теоретическая информация о том, как обучать борцов дзюдо качеству ловкости и реакции выбора в их обучении боевым искусствам, а также о том, как их тренировать.

Ключевые слова: Дзюдо, слепые, и слабовидящие, воспитывают у подростков избирательную реакцию, общую физическую подготовленность, специальную физическую подготовленность, физические качества, ловкость, быстроту.

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the work: after the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a great emphasis was placed on the development of physical education and sports. The tremendous reforms in the field of sports and the high results achieved were carried out by the president of our country Sh. It is the product of the rational state policy pursued by Mirziyoev. The establishment of Olympic and Paralympic Reserve colleges in the form of an educational institution corresponding to the 5th level of the international standard classifier of Education on the basis of the Olympic Reserve colleges PQ-5279 by our president on November 5, 2021, from the academic year 2022-2023 to September 1, 2022.

The contingent of Olympic and Paralympic Reserve colleges is only further improvement in Olympic and Paralympic sports.

At the same time, the further development of the field of physical education and sports is also a priority issue. The choice presented in this topic is the reaction and the importance of its development, while it is impossible to consider the basis that the athlete will achieve a high result, since the sport of judo is based on agility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main goal of this work is to determine the means and methods of nurturing the reaction of choice manifested in the sports of blind and weak-sighted adolescent judo.

Tasks for solving our case are also drawn up based on the purpose.

They are:

1) the study of simple and complex reactionaries in blind and vulnerable adolescent judokas.

2) description of methods and means of training in blind and weak-sighted teenage athletes.

The meaning of the word judo also summarizes the experience of different schools, systematizing the best techniques and making life – threatening judo-meaning "soft way".

To improve such decisions, first of all, Paralympic sports are not just, among the tasks in it are the further improvement of the activities of Sports and educational institutions, the introduction of a digitized new system of identifying, selecting and qualifying talented young people (selection), the creation of a strong Olympic reserve of athletes at the Olympic and Paralympic, Asian and Paraas games, in order to ensure participation and high performance in World Championships and other major international competitions, it is required to place physically handicapped and blind and weak vision points that are being sent to the respective Paralympic sports sections and exercises that help a teenage athlete to be able to do the right choice reaction. We provide relevant information on the reactions shown by blind and weak-sighted adolescent judokas and its relevance to the quality of agility.

Agility-F in a number of literature on the theory and methodology of Physical Culture. A.Kerimov M.N.Umarov. R.D.Kholmukhamedov L.L.Arapetiaisi P.Eugene .R.M.Matkarimov R.S.The scientific data presented in the lesson and literature of salmovs has been suggested to be considered as an aspect of being able to adapt quickly so that individual parts(fragments) of the organism, their systems can assimilate the necessary actions so that they have vital-necessary, professional-practical qualifications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The conditions of movement that arise when mastering any movement are called Agility, the ability to quickly, in the short term, adapt to the performance of movements, depending on the situation. To train agility, the system of previously learned, accustomed to performing movements is replaced by new ones, and other elements are added to the acquired movement. This in turn ensures a high level of “creative” activity of the cranial hemispheres.

This process is established through training, wellness training, tools of healthy lifestyle physical culture training gymnastics, jumping and throwing types of athletics, aquatics exercises, etc.

We need to know the simplest educational techniques used in the development of agility.

They are:

- the sound given after the blind and weak-sighted teenage judokas have “relaxed” the muscles to the point of telling them, the act of action agreed according to the sound or the performance of the action activity;

- blind and weak-sighted teenage judokas develop agility complexly by adding agility with other qualities, and the use of methods of struggle, competition gives a good result.

M.A.According to church research, agility manifests differently when performing professional or physical actions. This quality is closely related to the aspect of high development of individ muscles and the plasticity, rapid occurrence and exchange of processes in the bark of hemispheres. Agility also depends on joint mobility. As a result of studies and observations, it was determined that the period of 12-14 years is the most favorable period for the development of agility. By the age of 15-16, the formation of joint mobility slows down. That is why the exercise of the development of agility and its development largely assumes that teenage judokas spend a considerable amount of time in the training process. For the development of agility, it is advisable to use more games: blind and weak-sighted special checkered nests. Special character games the importance of agility-speed is also not secondary. Because agility does not manifest without speed.

And the development of agility forms the vital-necessary practical skills of movement, such as being able to adapt to the rapidly changing playing conditions, being able to observe, be able to aim correctly, to come to a clear, Stop, feel it in various complex situations in a short time. Improving the efficiency of the bike, using Action Tools, games also develop agility.

The coordination complexity of movements is the first measure of agility. If the spatial, temporal, force characteristics of an action are consistent with the action task, the action becomes clear enough. Hara kat tasks give rise to the concept of accuracy of movement. The accuracy of the movement is the second measure of agility.

Increasing the load directed towards the development of agility increases coordination difficulties for those who engage. During training, such difficulties are divided into three groups:

1. Difficulties in achieving the accuracy of actions.
2. Difficulties in their ability to adapt.
3. Hardships that are encountered unexpectedly, in a short time, in changed circumstances.

By educating athletes about the quality of agility, it will be possible to easily train even the choice reactions from oneself.

The reactions shown by the athlete are divided into two:

1. Simple reaction
2. Decomposes into complex reactions.

This is simple if a blind and weak-sighted adolescent judoka shows a response reaction to a slapped shutak heel because it would be a case of multiple tushintiril in the training process and being challenged by the rules of wrestling. Or if the judoka shows any javab reaction to defend against a given blow from the attack zone this complex reaction will be a selection reaction i.e., and the use of the above methods and tools in its development will give the most useful result.

CONCLUSION

Sports training is considered a much more comprehensive process, since there are many taps of preparation in it. In order to properly educate Manashu tamons, the coach is forced to take into account many aspects. The better the activity the athlete's nervous system performs, the more stagnation in movement will be persistent and positive. At this point, considering that the sport of judo requires speed and agility, we believe that turning young judokas from youth to being able to correctly assess the process and give the reaction of choice in time will serve as a foundation for the future result to be high.

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